

Cut-off	Study	Summary statistics
>2.5	Bender (5.75)	
	Bonac (9.98)	SE = 0.75 (0.64; 0.84)
	Guibourdenche (2.5)	SP = 0.83 (0.71; 0.91)
	Resch (6)	